

Infinite Product Formula Involving the Glaisher's Constant

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Abstract

We prove an infinite product formula related to the Glaisher's constant A using series involving Riemann Zeta functions.

1 Introduction

Glaisher's constant A is defined as:

$$A = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1^1 \cdot 2^2 \cdot 3^3 \cdots n^n}{n^{\frac{n^2}{2} + \frac{n}{2} + \frac{1}{12}} \cdot e^{-\frac{n^2}{4}}} = 1.282427129100622 \dots$$

Guillera and Sondow [1, Example 5.2] show the following product involving the Glaisher-Kinkelin constant:

$$\frac{A^{12}}{2^{4/3}e} = \left(\frac{2}{1}\right)^{2/2} \left(\frac{2^2}{1 \cdot 3}\right)^{3/4} \left(\frac{2^3 \cdot 4}{1 \cdot 3^3}\right)^{4/8} \left(\frac{2^4 \cdot 4^4}{1 \cdot 3^6 \cdot 5}\right)^{5/16} \cdots$$

In this paper, we demonstrate another infinite product formula for the mentioned expression through the use of series involving the Riemann zeta function.

Theorem 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{A^{12}}{2^{4/3}e} &= e \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{4k^2 - 1}\right)^{4k} \left(1 - \frac{2}{2k + 1}\right) \\
&= e \left(\frac{4}{3}\right)^4 \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{16}{15}\right)^8 \left(\frac{3}{5}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{36}{35}\right)^{12} \left(\frac{5}{7}\right) \cdots \\
&= 2.88884706667077 \dots
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. We start by considering the series:

$$\begin{aligned}
S &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[\log \left(1 - \frac{1}{2k}\right) - \log \left(1 + \frac{1}{2k}\right) - 4k \log \left(1 - \frac{1}{4k^2}\right) \right] \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[-2 \left(\operatorname{arccoth}(2k) + 2k \log \left(1 - \frac{1}{4k^2}\right) \right) \right].
\end{aligned}$$

The Taylor series expansion of $\operatorname{arccoth}(x)$ and the natural logarithm function $\log(x)$ are given by:

$$\operatorname{arccoth}(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)x^{2n+1}}, \quad |x| > 1, \quad \log(1-x) = -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n}, \quad |x| < 1.$$

Therefore, S can be expanded into a double sum:

$$\begin{aligned}
S &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{k^{-2n-1}}{(n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} - \frac{k^{-2n-1}}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} \right] \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{-k^{-2n-1}}{n \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n-1}}{(n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n-1}}{n \cdot 2^{2n}} - \frac{2k^{-2n-1}}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n-1}}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} \right] \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{-k^{-2n-1}}{n(n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n-1}}{n(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n-1}}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} \right] \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{-k^{-2n-1}}{(n+1)(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n-1}}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Now we define the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(n)$ as:

$$\zeta(n) = \sum_{k \geq 1} \frac{1}{k^n}, \quad \Re(n) > 1.$$

This expression allows us to transform S into the following sum:

$$S = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{-\zeta(2n+1)}{(n+1)(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} \right].$$

Using results from Srivastava and Choi [2, 572, p. 325] and [2, 156, p. 281] respectively, we find

$$-\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{(n+1)(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} = 12 \log(A) + \gamma - 2 - \frac{7}{3} \log(2)$$

and

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta(2n+1)}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} = \log(2) - \gamma$$

Thus,

$$S = 12 \log(A) - 2 - \frac{4}{3} \log(2).$$

□

A curious fact about this expression is that it suggests a close relationship with Apéry's constant. Specifically, when considering each individual factor raised to the power k , as obtained in our previous work by A. G. Llorente [3]:

$$\frac{e^{\frac{7\zeta(3)}{2\pi^2}}}{\sqrt{2}} = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{4k^2 - 1} \right)^{4k} \left(1 - \frac{2}{2k + 1} \right) \right]^k.$$

References

- [1] J. Guillera and J. Sondow, *Double integrals and infinite products for some classical constants via analytic continuations of Lerch's transcendent*, Ramanujan J. 16 (2008), 243–270.
- [2] H. M. Srivastava and Junesang Choi, *Introduction and Preliminaries*, in *Zeta and q-Zeta Functions and Associated Series and Integrals*, H. M. Srivastava and Junesang Choi (eds.), Elsevier, London, 2012, pp. 1–140. ISBN: 978-0-12-385218-2
- [3] A. G. Llorente. Infinite Product Formula Involving the Apéry's Constant, preprint, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13684827>